

STS-Med
Small scale thermal solar
district units for Mediterranean
communities
Ref. I-A/2.3/174

WP6. SUBTASK 6.2.4. EXECUTIVE DESIGN OF PILOT UNITS

The Cyprus Institute

DECEMBER 12, 2015
THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE
Nicosia, Cyprus

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CBCMED
CROSS-SECTOR COOPERATION
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

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EUROPEAN UNION

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5 Jordan -Millennium Energy 22

1 Introduction

This report gathers the executive drawings of design of the four units, for each of the sites, considering the adaptation of the site, the civil works needs and the specific authorizations to be obtained. The drawings provided correspond to the state of the art at the date of the report and the drawings of future implementation. This report describes the integration of the elements listed in task 6.1.3. “Design of the components and subsystems to be constructed”. The four pilot plants are supported by solar concentrators: Fresnel (Cyprus, Italy and Egypt) and parabolic collector (Jordan). The purpose of each plant is to provide cooling with absorption chillers. The systems in Egypt and Italy produce also electricity with Organic Rankine Cycle. In Jordan a steam turbine produces electricity with a steam turbine.

2 Cyprus – The Cyprus Institute

2.1 Linear Fresnel collector

2.2 Loops

2.3 Absorption chiller

3.3 General system

3.4 Oil loop

GENERAL NOTES:
 1--All dimensions in m

DATE	ISSUE
NO. 1	ISSUE
NO. 2	ISSUE
NO. 3	ISSUE
NO. 4	ISSUE
NO. 5	ISSUE
NO. 6	ISSUE
NO. 7	ISSUE
NO. 8	ISSUE
NO. 9	ISSUE
NO. 10	ISSUE
NO. 11	ISSUE
NO. 12	ISSUE
NO. 13	ISSUE
NO. 14	ISSUE
NO. 15	ISSUE
NO. 16	ISSUE
NO. 17	ISSUE
NO. 18	ISSUE
NO. 19	ISSUE
NO. 20	ISSUE
NO. 21	ISSUE
NO. 22	ISSUE
NO. 23	ISSUE
NO. 24	ISSUE
NO. 25	ISSUE
NO. 26	ISSUE
NO. 27	ISSUE

Project Name
 solar powered small scale
 poly-generation plant

CONSULTANT
 STSMED

ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner
 SEEKAM

Contractor

 ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
 75 MUSTAFA BENMANSOUR ST.
 TEL: 0222713814
 FAX: 0226702230

DRAWING NAME
 SHOP DRAWING FOR
 PLANT LAYOUT PART(S/3)

DWG. NO. A-03

SUB. NO. PV-00

SCALE : N.T.S

Date 4/6/2015

SHEET NO(S/3) 5-8-01

DRAWING BY ENG. ABD ELRAHMAN MUHAMMED

REVISED BY ENG. SAYED ELGHAREYB

3.5 Oil tank

GENERAL NOTES:
1-All dimensions in mm

NO.	DATE
1	ISSUED
2	APPROVED AND CORRECTED
3	APPROVED ONLY FOR PRINTING

Project Name:
SUPPLY AND INSTALLATION OF SERVICE OF PLANT MATERIAL

CONSULTANT:
STSMED STS med
ELECTRIC
ELSEWEDY ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner:
SEKAM

Contractor:
79 MONTAFA ELBAHARI ST.
ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
TEL:0027108114
FAX:002702000

DRAWING NAME:
Hot Oil Storage Tank

DRW. NO.	A-01
REV. NO.	REV 00
SCALE	1:1
Date	4/2/2016
Sheet no	0-2-02
DRAWING BY	ENG. AND ELBAHARI MOHAMMED
APPROVED BY	ENG. SAYED ELBAHARI

3.6 Oil pumps

LFR system Oil pump(3)

ORC system Oil pump(5)

FLOW METER(0-250L/min)

Chiller system Oil pump(6)

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	QUANTITY
2	FLEXIBLE CONNECTION		2
3	PRESSURE GAUGE		2
4	BALL VALVE		2
5	GATE VALVE		1
6	CHECK VALVE		1

GENERAL NOTES:

1-All dimensions in mm

REV.	DATE	BY	CHKD.
001	01/01/2015	STSMED	STSMED
002	01/01/2015	STSMED	STSMED
003	01/01/2015	STSMED	STSMED

Project Name:
 SUPPLY AND INSTALLATION OF
 SERVICE OF PLANT MATERIAL

CONSULTANT:
 STSMED STS med
 ELECTRIC
 ELSEWEDY ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner:
 SERKAM

Contractor:
 75 MOSTAFA ELBARADEI ST.
 ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
 TEL:002118114.
 FAX:00210380.

DRAWING NAME:
 OIL PUMPS DETAILS
 AND FLOW METER

DWG. NO.	A-01
REV. NO.	rev 00
SCALE	N.T.S
Date	4/9/2015
Sheet no	3-8-00
DRAWING BY	ENG. ABD ELRAHMAN MOHAMED
REVIEWED BY	ENG. ALYER ELGHARIB

3.7 Absorption chiller and Organic Rankine Cycle

3.8 Organic Rankine Cycle

3.9 Cooling tower of the Organic Rankine Cycle

3.10 Water pumps

Chilled Water Pump(7)

Chiller Condenser Water Pump(8)

ORC Condenser Water Pump(9)

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	QUANTITY
1	STRAINER		1
2	FLEXIBLE CONNECTION		2
3	PRESSURE GAUGE		2
4	BALL VALVE		2
5	GATE VALVE		1
6	CHECK VALVE		1

GENERAL NOTES:

1-All dimensions in mm

REV	DATE	BY	APP
001			
002			
003			
004			
005			
006			
007			
008			
009			
010			

Project Name:
SUPPLY AND INSTALLATION OF SERVICE OF PLANT MATERIAL

CONSULTANT:
 STS med
 ELECTRIC
 ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner:
SEBKAM

Contractor:
 TO MOSTAFA ELHABASH ST.
 ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
 TEL: 022210114.
 FAX: 022210228.

DRAWING NAME:
WATER PUMPS DETAILS

FIG. NO.	1-22
REV. NO.	REV. 00
SCALE	N.T.S
Date	4/16/2016
Sheet no	2-2-10
DRAWING BY	ENG. ABD ELRAHMAN MOHAMMED
REVISED BY	ENG. HAYED ELGHARIB

3.11 Water loop

GENERAL NOTES:
 1-All dimensions in m

REV	DATE	DESCRIPTION

Project Name
 solar powered small scale
 poly-generation plant

CONSULTANT
 STSMED STS med
 ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner
 SEEKAM

Contractor
 ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
 76 MOSTAFA ELNABASH ST.
 TEL. 0225713814.
 FAX. 0226702630.

DRAWING NAME:
 SHOP DRAWING FOR
 PLANT LAYOUT PART(1/3)

DWG. NO.	A-03
SUB. NO.	rev 00
SCALE :	N.T.S
Date	4/6/2015
SHEET NO(1/3)	S-E-01
DRAWING BY	ENG: ABD ELRAHMAN MOHAMED
REVISED BY	ENG: SAYED ELGHAREIB

3.12 Water tanks

3.13 Absorption chiller

3.14 Absorption chiller cooling tower

GENERAL NOTES:
 1-All dimensions in mm

REV	NO	DATE
1	1	04/08/16
2	1	04/08/16
3	1	04/08/16

Project Name:
 SUPPLY AND INSTALLATION OF SERVICE OF PLANT MATERIAL

CONSULTANT:
 STSMED STS med
 ELECTRIC
 ELSEWEDY ELSEWEDY ELECTRIC

Owner:
 SERKAM

Contractor:
 TO MOUTAZI BAKHARAH BY ELHUDA CONTRACTING CO.
 TEL:009715814. FAX:009715814.

DRAWING NAME:
 CHILLER COOLING TOWER DETAILS

DRW. NO.	1-03
REV. NO.	REV. 00
SCALE	1:1
Date	4/8/2016
Sheet no	2-8-11

DRAWING BY: ENG. ABD ELRAHMAN MOHAMMED
 REVIEWED BY: ENG. HAYED ELBAHARAD

4 Italy - ARCA

4.1 Layout

4.2 Project plan

5 Jordan -Millennium Energy

